

method of Drake and Bronitsky (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 3715). The ester melted at 101.2° and its melting point was not altered by mixing it with a pure sample of the *p*-phenylphenacyl ester of lignoceric acid.

SUMMARY.

As a result of the detailed chemical examination of the oil from the seeds of *Datura stramonium*, the following constituents were identified:

Unsaturated acids—Oleic and linolic acids.

Saturated acids—Palmitic and stearic acids together with a small quantity of lignoceric acid. No daturic acid could be detected.

A phytosterol, melting at 134°, was obtained from the unsaponifiable matter.

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Parachor and Chemical Constitution. Part III. The Structure of Urea and Thiourea.

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The extensive researches carried out by Werner ("The Chemistry of Urea," Longmans, Green & Co., London, 1923) led him to doubt the validity of the carbamide formula, so universally accepted by chemists to represent the constitution of urea, and to propose a cyclic formula for urea (and thiourea) in the static condition or when present in a neutral solvent.

The object of the present investigations is to find out which of the following two structures agrees with the parachor contribution of the urea and thiourea molecules:

The surface tension was determined by the method of maximum

I—Formamide; II—MeOH; III—EtOH.

bubble pressure as in the previous works. In these experiments, xylene was employed as the manometer liquid, instead of alcohol, and was found to give better results. As the compounds decompose on fusion, the surface tension and density were determined in solution and the parachor calculated from the results obtained (*cf.* Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 671).

The parachor study of urea and of thiourea particularly in solution was found to be extremely limited owing to the lack of suitable solvents. It will be seen that in aqueous solutions constant parachor values were obtained in low concentrations. With increase of concentration after a cer-

tain limit, the parachor was found to diminish owing probably to association between the solute and the solvent molecules. In formamide, methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol, the parachor was found to increase with the increase of x . In these cases the required values are obtained by drawing curves, by plotting P_x against x , and finding its point of intersection with the x axis. In pyridine the values are also not constant. With increasing concentration of the solute, the parachor increases and becomes some what constant.

It will be evident from the results given in the following tables that the parachor contributions of urea and thiourea in aqueous solution and of urea in formamide agree with the carbamide structure. The parachor value of urea, both in methyl and ethyl alcohols, was found to be about 125. This low value is supposed to be due to association between the solute molecules or between the solute and the

solvent molecules. This was corroborated by determining the molecular weight of urea in methyl and ethyl alcohols by Will and Bredig's method of the lowering of the vapour pressure (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1084). It was found that the molecular weight of urea in alcoholic solution is not normal but increases rapidly with increase of concentration. But the exact molecular weight cannot be definitely settled, hence no deduction can be drawn from these results. In pyridine the value was found to be about 144 and here also it is not possible to arrive at any definite conclusion.

In the following tables, x denotes the mol fraction of the solute, M_m , the mean M. W. of the solution, P_m , the mean parachor and P_x , the parachor of the solute. The values within parentheses are obtained from the curves given in the previous page. The observations were carried out between the temperature of 28-30°.

TABLE I

Urea in water.

$P_{\text{calc.}}$ for open and ring structure are respectively 141.4 and 158.1.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	0.9991	74.56	18	52.94	—
0.01326	1.009	74.69	18.56	54.09	139.5
0.01862	1.012	74.71	18.79	54.59	141.3
0.02125	1.014	74.77	18.90	54.81	141.2
0.02314	1.016	74.74	18.99	54.99	140.4
0.03556	1.024	74.85	19.49	55.94	137.3
0.03701	1.028	75.09	19.56	56.01	138.7
0.03806	1.031	75.11	19.60	56.03	134.0
0.05921	1.047	75.34	20.44	57.49	135.7
0.06868	1.054	75.48	20.88	58.41	132.8
0.08443	1.068	74.99	21.55	59.39	129.2

TABLE II.

Urea in formamide.

$P_{\text{calc.}}$ for open and ring formulae are respectively 141.4 and 158.1.

$x.$	Density.	Surface tension.	$M_m.$	$P_m.$	$P_x.$
0.0	1.159	62.67	45	109.2	—
0.02622	1.662	62.64	45.39	109.8	132.6
0.03101	1.164	62.60	45.46	109.8	129.0
0.03824	1.166	62.58	45.58	110.0	128.1
0.04735	1.168	69.47	45.70	110.0	124.7
0.05853	1.171	62.37	45.87	110.1	123.0
1.0	—	—	—	—	(141.8)

TABLE III.

Urea in methyl alcohol.

$P_{\text{calc.}}$ for open and ring formulae are respectively 141.4 and 158.1.

$x.$	Density.	Surface tension.	$M_m.$	$P_m.$	$P_x.$
0.0	0.7883	22.32	32	88.22	—
0.02880	0.8060	22.94	32.81	89.10	118.4
0.04509	0.8244	23.98	33.26	89.30	112.2
0.05480	0.8320	24.21	33.53	89.39	109.5
0.06756	0.8416	24.32	33.89	89.43	106.1
0.08000	0.8503	24.42	34.24	89.50	104.3
0.08194	0.8531	24.55	34.29	89.45	103.4
0.1028	0.8708	24.67	34.88	89.10	98.51
1.0	—	—	—	—	(125.0)

TABLE IV.

Urea in ethyl alcohol.

$P_{\text{calc.}}$ for open and ring formulae are respectively 141.4 and 158.1.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	0.7829	21.86	46	127.1	—
0.01037	0.7882	22.11	46.15	127.0	119.4
0.01547	0.7911	22.25	46.22	126.9	116.3
0.02054	0.7934	22.28	46.29	126.8	112.0
0.02554	0.7950	22.30	46.36	126.7	109.6
0.03232	0.7997	22.30	46.45	126.3	105.2
0.04007	0.8039	22.45	46.57	126.1	102.3
1.0	—	—	—	—	(125.7)

TABLE V.

Thiourea in water.

$P_{\text{calc.}}$ for open and ring formulae are respectively 196.6 and 186.3.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	0.9988	74.41	18	52.94	—
0.002949	1.002	74.30	18.18	53.27	169.2
0.005832	1.004	74.31	18.33	53.62	168.1
0.005883	1.004	74.36	18.34	53.63	169.8
0.007028	1.006	74.43	18.41	53.75	168.0
0.009674	1.009	74.56	18.56	54.06	169.3
0.01085	1.012	74.98	18.63	54.20	169.6
0.01396	1.015	75.03	18.81	54.55	168.4
0.01457	1.016	75.10	18.85	54.62	168.6
0.01738	1.019	75.01	19.01	54.92	166.9
0.01791	1.020	74.99	19.01	54.94	164.7

TABLE VI.

Thiourea in pyridine.

$P_{\text{calc.}}$ for open and ring formulae are respectively 169.6 and 186.3.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	0.9738	36.11	79	198.8	—
0.02054	0.9835	36.51	78.94	197.2	121.7
0.03247	0.9874	36.75	78.89	196.7	135.5
0.04214	0.9904	36.39	78.88	196.3	140.1
0.06132	0.9979	37.58	78.82	195.5	145.2
0.07741	1.005	37.82	78.77	194.4	142.1
0.08561	1.007	37.87	78.75	194.1	143.6
0.09493	1.012	38.45	78.70	193.7	145.4
0.1019	1.015	38.16	78.69	192.8	140.4

SUMMARY.

The surface tension and density of urea and thiourea were determined in solution and the parachor calculated. The parachor values were found to agree with the carbamide structure.

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